

Angiosperm Flora of Some Species in Kalaw Area

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Abstract

Some Angiospermae from Kalaw area has been collected identified and then morphological characteristic were studied. In this study, 10 species belonging to 10 genera of 9 families were identified and systematically arranged with colored plates. All species are dicotyledonous. Artificial key to the species, detail description of the individual species and uses has also been described. In addition, their flowering period, Myanmar names and English names were also described.

Key words: Angiosperm, Kalaw area

Introduction

The region of Kalaw is situated in Southern Shan State. It lies between $17^{\circ}16'$ - $17^{\circ}17'$ North Latitude and $96^{\circ}29'$ - $96^{\circ}30'$ East Longitude. Kalaw lies 1320 meter above sea level. It is 70 kilometer west of Taunggyi about halfway along the Thazi-Taunggyi road. The area of Kalaw is approximately about 40 square mile. Kalaw is a hill town located on the rolling hill of Shan Plateau. It is a peaceful and quiet place. It is also pleasantly cool and a good place for hiking amid gnarled pines, bamboo groves and rugged mountain scene.

In 2015, an average monthly rainfall is 4 mm. The maximum rain fall occurred in June and September (18 mm). The minimum rain fall occurred in April and August (3 mm) and the area almost get no rainfall in January, February, March, May, July, October and December. The maximum temperature is 43°C (June) and minimum temperature is 34.5°C (March). During the period from January to June 2016, the maximum temperature is 35.8°C (May) and the minimum temperature is 20°C (January).

Yellowish red to ferruginous soil or red-earth are found in the study area.

The climatic condition of Kalaw area is the temperate zone. The natural vegetation of Kalaw area consists of herbs, shrubs, climbers, twiners, vines and woody trees. The families Papaveraceae, Rosaceae, Capparaceae, Plumbaginaceae, Loganiaceae, Bignoniaceae, Verbenaceae, Convolvulaceae and Solanaceae are found in this area. The Rosaceae was commonly found in this area. The family Plumbaginaceae was rarely found in the study area.

In the present study 10 species belonging to 10 genera of 9 families under subclass Magnoliidae had been identified and fully described with uses.

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Fig.1. Location map of Kalaw area

Materials and Methods

Some members of Angiosperm were collected from Kalaw area. The specimens were collected from 1st to 4th, April, 2016. The specimens were kept immediately into the plastic bags to identify and classify systematically. The collected specimens had been observed and noted in detail. In addition to construction of artificial key to the species, all the resulting species are systematically arranged into family according to APG III system, 2009 (Angiosperm Phylogeny Group). The specimens were recorded by photographs. The collected specimens were identified with the references of Flora of British India (Hooker, 1881-87), Flora of Java (Backer, 1965) and Flora of Ceylon (Dassanayake, 1980-2001).

Results

**Table. List of the collected species
Angiosperm (Subclass : Magnoliidae)**

Super order	Order	Family	No.	Scientific name	Myanmar name
Eudicots	Ranunculales	Papaveraceae	1.	<i>Argemone mexicana</i> L.	Kha-ya
Fabids	Rosales	Rosaceae	2.	<i>Fragaria vesca</i> L.	Strawberry
Malvids	Brassicales	Capparaceae	3.	<i>Crateva magna</i> (Lour.) DC.	Kon-kadet
	Caryophyllales	Plumbaginaceae	4.	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i> L.	Kant-gyok-phyu
Lamids	Gentianales	Loganiaceae	5.	<i>Buddleja asiatica</i> Lour.	Kyaung-mee-gu
	Lamiales	Bignoniaceae	6.	<i>Jacaranda ovalifolia</i> R.Br.	Sein-pan-pya
			7.	<i>Pyrostegia venusta</i> Miers.	Shwe-let-chaung
		Verbenaceae	8.	<i>Clerodendrum viscosum</i> Vent.	Pet-kha
	Solanales	Convolvulaceae	9.	<i>Ipomoea indica</i> (Burf.) Merr.	Unknown
Solanaceae		10.	<i>Brugmansia suaveolens</i> (Humb. & Bonpl. ex Willd) Bercht & Presl.	Padaing-gyi	

An artificial key to the studied species:

1. Placentation parietal or pendulous.....2
1. Placentation axile.....5
 2. Placentation parietal3
 2. Placentation pendulous.....4

3. Herb; leaves base subamplexicaul; flowers yellow.....**1. *Argemone mexicana***
3. Tree; leaves base oblique; flowers white or cream.....**3. *Crateva magna***
4. Leaves simple; stamens 5.....**4. *Plumbago zeylanica***
4. Leaves compound; stamens numerous.**2. *Fragaria vesca***
5. Flowers actinomorphic.....6
5. Flowers zygomorphic.....8
6. Twining herb; flowers bluish purple.....**9. *Ipomoea indica***
6. Shrub; flowers white or creamy white.....7
7. Calyx campanulate; stamens 5.....**10. *Brugmansia suaveolens***
7. Calyx spathe-like; stamens 4.....**5. *Buddleja asiatica***
8. Leaves simple; fruit drupaceous.....**8. *Clerodendrum viscosum***
8. Leaves compound; fruit capsular.....9
9. Tree, flowers purplish blue.....**6. *Jacaranda ovalifolia***
9. Tendrillar climber; flowers bright orange..... **7. *Pyrostegia venusta***

Taxonomic descriptions

Papaveraceae (Juss. 1789)

1. *Argemone mexicana* L., Sp. Pl. 508. 1753.

Myanmar name	-	Kha-ya, Plate 1 (A)
English name	-	Mexican poppy; Prickly poppy
Flowering period	-	April to July

Annual, erect, prickly herbs, up to 1 m high; stems and branches terete, robust, glabrous. Leaves simple, alternate, exstipulate; sessile; blades oblong or obovate, 4.5-11 cm by 2.5-9 cm, irregularly pinnatifid, with white prickles on the nerves of both surfaces, subamplexicaul at the base, spinose-dentate along the margin, acute and spinous at the apex, glaucous. Flowers usually terminal and solitary, bright yellow, 4.7 cm in diameter, actinomorphic, subtended by 1-3 spinous bracts. Sepals 2 or 3, free, oblong, 1 cm by 0.7 cm, convex, spinous, caducous. Petals 4 or 6, free, obovate, 2-2.5 cm long, crumpled in bud, fugacious. Stamens numerous, free, included; filament filiform; 6-7 mm long; anthers dithecous, 2.3 mm long. Ovary superior, ovoid, 6-9 mm long, soft-spinous, unilocular, with numerous ovules on 3-6 parietal placentae; styles sessile; stigma 5-lobed. Capsules oblong, 3.5-4 cm by 1.5-2 cm, many-seeded, spinose, dehiscent apically 3-7 valves. Seed subspherical, 1 mm in diameter, blackish, pitted.

Distribution : Pantropic weed of cultivation and disturbed ground (Philcox as cited in Dassanayake, 1999). According to Kress *et al.* (2003) recorded that this species was distributing in Kachin State, Mandalay Division and Sagaing Division of Myanmar.

Uses : As a whole the plant has been conceded to be anodyne, deterrent, resolutive, hypnotic, diuretic, diaphoretic, ophthalmic, and a hydragogue cathartic. The latex juice of the plant was mixed with water for skin diseases, and the flowers used for chest complaints and as a narcotic. Its leaves decoction is used to cure malarial fever and ulcers. Its root is diuretic, anodyne and is used in chronic skin diseases. Its seeds are laxative, expectorant

and demulcent. The juice of the plant is used to jaundice. Its latex is used to treat cataract, reddening and itching in the eyes. Oil extracted from its seeds is very toxic and must not be consumed.

Rosaceae (Juss. 1789)

2. *Fragaria vesca* L. Sp. 494. 1753.

Myanmar name	-	Strawberry Plate 1 (B)
English name	-	Strawberry
Flowering period	-	February to April

Perennial herbs; stolons slender creeping. Leaves palmately trifoliolate compound, alternate; stipules 1.2-3.5 cm long; tapering at end, membranous sheathing; petioles 1-11 cm long; leaflets broadly ovate, 3.2-7.5 cm by 2.8-6.5 cm, cuneate or obtuse at the base, crenate serrate along the margin; acute at the apex, soft herbaceous, bright green above, paler with very short inconspicuous glandular hairs beneath. Inflorescences usually 3-flowered erect cyme or solitary, pilose. Scapes equal to or longer than the leaves, pilose. Flowers white, about 2.2 cm in diameter, actinomorphic; bracts trifid at the apex, foliaceous; pedicels up to 1.5 cm long, becoming longer in fruits. Epicalyx 5-lobed, lobes 3.6 cm long, acute, pilose outside. Calyx 5-lobed, lobes 5.2-7.3 mm long, acuminate. Petals 5, obovate, 3.8-5.8 mm long, spreading, white. Stamens numerous; filaments filiform; anthers ditheous. Carpels numerous, free, placed on a high convex and fleshy receptacle, pale green when immature, pinkish red and much enlarged and juicy when mature; style lateral, deciduous. Fruits etaerio of achenes, obovoid, 2.2-2.6 cm, bright red; fruiting epicalyx and calyx lobes reflexed, spreading in the ripe fruits; achenes numerous, smooth, seated in pits on the oblong or globose, red or pinkish white receptacle.

Distribution : Cultivated in most temperate regions of the world. In Ceylon, cultivated in Horton Plains and in Hakgala (Tirvengadumt as cited in Dassanayake, 1981). Kress *et al.* (2003) stated that this species was distributing in Chin State, Kachin State and Mandalay Division of Myanmar.

Uses : The strawberry is a useful dentifrice and cosmetic. The fresh fruit removes discoloration of the teeth of the juice is allowed to remain on for about five minute and the teeth are then cleaned with warm water. A cut strawberry rubbed over the face immediated after washing will whiten the skin and remove slight sunburns. The leaves of the wild strawberry plant are gently astringent in nature and hence are used as a diuretic to enhance the outflow of urine. While the leaves are boiled in water and used as a gargle to treat acting throat, they also form an important ingredient in some lotions used to treat burns and scratches on the skin. The leaves of the strawberry plant use as tuberculosis, arthritis, gout and rheumatism or joint pains.

Capparaceae (Juss. 1989)

3. *Crateva magna* (Lour.) DC. Prod. 1: 243. 1824.

Myanmar name	-	Kadet; Kon-kadet, Plate 1 (C)
English name	-	Three leaves caper
Flowering period	-	March to May

Perennial, erect, spreading trees, up to 21 m high; stem terete, branches cylindrical, glabrous, with white warts. Leaves palmately trifoliolate compound, alternate; stipules small; petioles 4-7.5 cm long, glabrous; leaflets 3, broadly elliptic or obliquely ovate, 5-15 cm by 3-7

cm, cuneate or oblique at the base, entire along the margin, acuminate at the apex, glabrous. Inflorescences terminal corymbose cyme; peduncles 8-16 cm long, glabrous. Flowers white or cream to yellow, 4.5 cm in diameter, actinomorphic, fragrant; bracts linear, 1.5-2 mm long, pubescent; pedicels 1.5-4 cm long, glabrous. Sepals 4, free, oblong or elliptic, 2-5 mm long, green, glabrous, patent. Petals 4, free, broadly ovate, obovate or oblong with a long claw, 1.7-3.5 cm by 1-2.2 cm, obtuse or rounded at the base, yellow or yellowish green with reticulate veins, glabrous above, pubescent beneath. Stamens numerous, free, adnate to the gynophore; filaments filiform, 1.5-5.2 cm long, pale yellow, glabrous; anthers dithecous, oblong, straight or curved, pale yellow or yellowish brown. Gynophore 2.5-6 cm long, glabrous. Disk cup-shaped and incurved. Ovary superior, ellipsoid, unilocular, with numerous 2-seriate ovules in each parietal placenta; style sessile; stigma depressed. Fruits baccate, ellipsoid, 2.5 cm in diameter, leathery, smooth when young, but soon covered with flat dry papillae, pendulous on the woody gynophore. Seeds large, reniform, black, smooth.

Distribution : India, Ceylon and Burma (Philcox as cited in Dassanayake, 1996). Kress *et al.* (2003) recorded that this species was widely distributed in Myanmar.

Uses : *Crataeva magna* tree is rich in nutrients. The young leaves are edible. *Crataeva magna* is used as cervical adenitis, abscess, enlarged spleen, edematous wounds. Three leaves caper is beneficial in the treatment of urinary tract infections, painful and burning urination, and urinary and kidney-stones. It expels out worms both from intestine and liver. It also decreases body's temperature in fever condition. It helps in treating anorexia. It also acts a liver tonic. It also cures rheumatic joint pain and edematous wounds. The decoction of bark is internally administered to cure diseases like renal calculi, dysuria, helminthiasis, inflammations and abscesses. The decoction exhibits actions like carminative, laxative, diuretic and expectorant.

Plumbaginaceae (Juss. 1789)

4. *Plumbago zeylanica* L., Sp. Pl. 15. 1753.

Myanmar name	-	Kant-gyok-phyu, Plate 1 (D)
English name	-	White leadwort
Flowering period	-	January to April

Perennial, straggling shrubs; branches cylindrical, up to 2 m high, glabrous, sometimes stem zig-zag. Leaves simple, alternate; exstipulate; petioles 1 cm long, dilated to form rounded, amplexicaul stipule-like auricles; auricles caducous, associated mainly with young leaves; blades ovate, 2.5-8 cm by 1.5-5.5 cm, obtuse at the base, undulate and entire along the margin; acute at the apex, thin, glabrous and scurfy beneath. Inflorescences axillary or terminal raceme, with few to numerous flowers; peduncles 5-32 cm long, copiously glandular. Flowers white, about 1.5 cm in diameter, actinomorphic; bracts ovate, 6 mm by 3 mm, acute, glandular; bracteoles 2, smaller than the bracts; pedicels about 1 mm long. Calyx tubular, 5-lobed, covered with large stalked, globose crimson-tipped green glands, persistent; tube 1.7 cm long; lobes linear, 1 cm long, equal. Corolla salverform, 5-lobed, twisted in bud, glabrous; tube 2 cm long; lobes obovate, 5-7 mm by 6 mm, truncate with a mucro at the apex, patent. Stamens 5, free, adnate below to the corolla, inserted; filaments filiform, 1.5 cm long, dilated at the base, white; anthers dithecous, oblong, purplish. Ovary superior, oblong, 5-angular, glabrous, unilocular, with solitary ovule on the pendulous placenta; style filiform, 1.5 mm long, white, glabrous; stigma 5. Capsules oblong, 1 cm long, 1-seeded, membranous within the persistent calyx, sharply pointed with 5 furrows. Seeds solitary, cylindrical, pendulous, dark purple, minute.

Distribution : Throughout the old world tropics (Abeynayake as cited in Dassanayake, 1997). According to Kress *et al.* (2003), this species was cultivated in Myanmar.

Uses : The juice from the roots were traditionally used to provide blue to black coloration for tattoos. The fruit and seed, sugar cane stems, and were also used to produce blue to black pigment. Plumbago is considered for its invasive medicinal properties such as anti-cancer activity, anti-fertility activity, anti-inflammatory activity, anti-microbial activity and anti-oxidant activity. It has many uses and is also valued as effective abortifacient herb. The paste of the whole plant is applied externally on any kind of skin disease, extract of leaves and root is administered orally to alleviate arthritic pain and the plant acts as a good digestive. Product 'muscle and joint rub' is highly effective for backaches, muscular sprains and joint pains.

Loganiaceae (R. Br. ex Mart. 1827)

5. *Buddleja asiatica* Lour., Fl. Cochinch. 72. 1790.

Myanmar name	-	Kyaung-mee-gu, Plate 1 (E)
English name	-	Butterfly bush
Flowering period	-	February to April

Perennial, erect shrubs, up to 2.5 m high; stems and branches terete or subterete, grey white or fulvous-tomentose. Leaves simple, opposite and decussate, exstipulate; petioles 2-6 mm long; blades lanceolate to oblong-lanceolate, 4.5-9 cm by 1.5-6 cm, attenuate at the base, entire along the margin, acuminate at the apex, densely white-tomentose beneath. Inflorescences terminal, erect paniculate spike drooping at the tip; peduncles 10-36 cm long, tomentose. Flowers white, 4 mm in diameter, sessile, actinomorphic, fragrant; bracts linear, 2.5 mm long; pedicels 2 mm long. Calyx campanulate, 4-lobed, 2 mm long; tube 1 mm long; lobes triangular, about 1 mm long, acute, densely pubescent outside. Corolla salverform, 4 lobed, pubescent; tube cylindrical, straight or curved, 5 mm long, whitish cream, pubescent outside; lobes subequal broadly ovate, about 2 mm long. Stamens 4, free, inserted above the middle of the corolla-tube; filaments about 1 mm long; anthers dithecous, ovate-oblong or sagittate, pale yellow. Ovary superior, ovoid, 1 mm long, glabrous, bilocular, with numerous ovules in each locule on the axile placentae; style linear, glabrous; stigma capitate. Capsules ellipsoid, about 6 mm long, 2-valved, many-seeded, glabrous. Seeds elliptic, minute, pale brown.

Distribution : Malaya, Cochin-China, and China (Hooker, 1885). According to Kress *et al.* (2003) stated that this species was widely distributed in Myanmar.

Uses : Wood is moderately hard, used for making walking sticks. The dried and powdered root is used in the preparation of fermented liquor. A yellow liquid obtained from boiling the flowers is used as a colouring for rice. *Buddleja* species are traditionally used in folk medicine as a topical antiseptic, a diuretic and abortive. *B. asiatica* is also used in perfumes as it produces a sweet freesia-like fragrance. The plant has been used as an abortifacient and also in the treatment of skin complaints. Paste of roots mixed with rice water used as tonic. Roots and leaves used to treat tumor-like growths. Concentrated infusion of roots used to treat malaria. Leaf paste applied to forehead for treatment of fever. For high fever in children, root extract is taken, and warm root extract is rubbed onto the whole body.

Bignoniaceae (Juss. 1789)

6. *Jacaranda ovalifolia* R. Br., Bot. Mag. t. 2327. 1822.

Myanmar name	-	Sein-pan-pya, Plate 1 (F)
English name	-	Green ebony
Flowering period	-	April to May

Deciduous trees, 10 m high, stems and branches terete or subangular, puberulous. Leaves bipinnate-compound, opposite and decussate, exstipulate; petioles and primary rachis 26-31 cm by 2.7-4.2 mm, puberulous, pulvinate at the base; secondary rachis alternate at the lower part, opposite at the upper part, 20-23 pairs, 2.5-12-7 cm long, puberulous; leaflets sessile variable in number on each secondary rachis, blades elliptic-oblong, 10.5-15.5 cm by 4.8-6.8 mm, obtuse at the base, entire along the margin, acute at the apex, terminal one 16-20 mm long, acute at the base, acuminate at the apex. Inflorescences axillary or terminal paniculate dichasial cymes. Flowers purplish blue, 1-2 cm in diameter, zygomorphic; bracts lanceolate, 4-5 mm long, glabrous, caducous; pedicels 6-10 mm long. Calyx broadly tubular 5-lobed, green; lobes 3-5 mm by 1 mm. Corolla funnellform, 5-lobed; tube curved, 6-10 mm by 1-2 mm; lobes ovate, 1-2 cm by 1-1.7 cm, rounded at the apex, with white spots around the mouth. Stamens 4, didynamous, epipetalous, inserted; filaments filiform, curved, the longer ones 1.3-1.8 cm long, white, puberulous at the base; anthers ditheous, unequal, white. Disk short, annular, greenish. Ovary superior, ovate, bilocular, with many ovules in each locule on the axile placentae; style filiform, pink, glabrous; stigma bifid. Capsules orbicular, 5 cm long, compressed, winged, many-seeded, woody, glabrous.

Distribution : This species was a native of Brazil and N.W Argentina. It was widely cultivated in warmer parts of the world (Nasir, 1979). According to Kress. *et al.* (2003), this species was cultivated in Myanmar.

Uses : The bark and roots are used in the treatment of syphilis. The timber is yellowish-white, hard, moderately heavy, fine textured, easy to work, and is used for carpentry. Wood is light brown and soft. It is used for poles and for making small item such as tool handles and carvings. Provides a useful firewood.

7. *Pyrostegia venusta* Miers, in Proc. Roy. Hort. Soc. 3. 186. 1863.

Myanmar name	-	Shwe-let-chaung, Plate 1 (G)
English name	-	Flame vine; Golden shower
Flowering period	-	February to April

Perennial, tendrillar climbers; stems and branches terete, with longitudinal furrow. Leaves unipinnate-compound, imparipinnate, opposite and decussate, exstipulate; petioles 1.5-3 cm long, pulvinate, pubescent; tendril long, 3-fid, fugacious, pubescent; leaflets 2-3, ovate, 2-8 cm by 1.5-3.7 cm, obtuse at the base, entire along the margin, acute at the apex, glabrous on both surfaces; petiolules 2-5 mm long. Inflorescences shortly peduncled cymes with 1-7 flowers. Flowers bright orange, 2.2 cm in diameter, zygomorphic; bracts caducous; pedicels 1.5 cm long. Calyx 5-lobed, yellowish-green; tube 5-7 mm long, much widened upwards, teeth linear, 0.6 mm long, equal. Corolla tubular, 5-lobed, hairy inside, glabrous outside; tube 6 cm long, narrow, widened and laterally compressed upwards; lobes oblong-linear, recurved, 1.5-2.5 cm long, 2 posterior ones connate about halfway up. Stamens 4, free, epipetalous, exerted; filaments filiform, 3.5-5 cm long, orange; anther ditheous, oblong, orange. Disk pale yellow, 4 mm in diameter. Ovary superior, oblongoid, about 6 mm long, glabrous, bilocular, with many ovules in each locule on the axile placentae; style filiform, about 5 cm long, yellowish green, glabrous; stigma lamellated. Capsules oblongoid, 21-26 cm long, many-seeded, glabrous. Seeds elliptic, membranous winged.

Distribution : This species was widespread in native to Brazil (Backer, 1934). According to Kress *et al.* (2003), this species was reported from Myanmar.

Uses : *Pyrostegia venusta* is cultivated throughout the tropics and subtropics as a popular ornamental and possibly naturalizing in some areas. *Pyrostegia venusta* is a native

brazilian plant, which has been used in traditional folk medicine as a remedy for treating leukoderma and vitiligo. The aerial parts of *Pyrostegia venusta* is useful for the treatment of cough and common diseases of the respiratory system related to infections, such as bronchitis, flu and cold. They administer its decoction orally as a general tonic, and also as an infusion to treat diarrhoea and jaundice. Tonic made from the stems of this plant are useful for the treatment of diarrhoea, whereas flower preparations have been shown to attenuate vomiting.

Verbenaceae (J. St. Hil . 1805)

8. *Clerodendrum viscosum* Vent., Jard.Malm. 1: 25, pl. 25. 1803.

Myanmar name - Pet-kha, **Plate 1 (H)**

English name - Unknown

Flowering period - January to April

Large stout undershrubs, or erect trees, 1-4 m high, bitter and fetid throughout; stems and branches slender, obtusely tetragonal, sparsely appressed pubescent. Leaves simple, opposite and decussate; exstipulate; petioles slender, 2-7.5 cm long, densely villous with appress flavescent hairs; blades broad elliptic-ovate or suborbicular, 5-19 cm by 7-17 cm, cordate at the base, dentate along the margin, acuminate at the apex, subcoriaceous, fulvous tomentose on both surfaces, more densely beneath. Inflorescences terminal panicle, few-flowered; peduncles 1-5 cm long, purplish red. Flowers white tinged with purplish pink, 2.5 cm in diameter, zygomorphic, fragrant; bracts elliptic, 3.7 cm by 1.2 cm, foliaceous, densely villous; bractoles linear, 2 mm by 1 mm, pubescent; pedicels about 4 mm long, purplish-red. Calyx campanulate, 5-lobed, bright-green during anthesis and then gradually changed into red; tube 1.4 cm long; lobes linear, 1cm long. Corolla tubular, 5-lobed, pubescent; tube cylindric, 2.7 cm long; lobes ovate-oblong, 1-1.5 cm long, glabrous. Stamens 4, free, didynamous, exserted; filaments filiform, 3.5-4 cm long, white, glabrous; anthers dithecous, elliptic-oblong, deep-purple to red. Ovary superior, globose, 2 mm long, tetralocular, one ovule in each locule on the axile placentae; style 2.2 cm long; stigma shortly bifid. Drup globose, 1 cm in diameter, 1-4 seeded, bluish-black or black, shiny, with accrescent, leathery, deep-red calyx.

Distribution : Kress *et al.* (2003) stated that this species was widely distributing in Myanmar.

Uses : Extract prepared from young leave is taken for the treatment of stomachache, dysentery and diarrhea. Leaves boiled in water and used to take bath in jaundice and scabies. Leaf is used as masticatory substance for the treatment of pain. Young leaves are taken for abdominal pain and pills prepared from leaves are taken for gastric ulcers. Paste prepared from leaves applied in infected area of children's head. Leaf extract is taken as anthelmintic, in addition cough and dysentery. A paste of the leaves is applied to affected areas for the treatment of head sores. Ash prepared from leaf, mixed with coconut oil is applied in the swelling leg and blister twice daily.

Convolvulaceae (Juss. 1789)

9. *Ipomoea indica* (Burf.) Merr., Int. Rumph. Herb. Amb. 445. 1917.

Myanmar name - Unknown, **Plate 1 (I)**

English name - Blue morning glory, Blue dawn flower

Flowering period - January to April

Annual or perennial herbs, twining or prostrate, terrestrial; stems cylindrical, solid, much branched, herbaceous to somewhat woody near the base, densely hirsute. Leave simple,

alternate, exstipulate; petioles 2-5cm long, hirsute; blades rounded ovate, 3-lobed, 5-11 cm by 3 -9.5 cm, cordate at the base, entire and ciliate along the margin, acute to silkly acuminate at the apex, densely appressed-hairy beneath, less pilose above. Inflorescences axillary umbellate cymes, 1 to 5- flowered; peduncles 1-4 cm long, silky white-pubescent. Flowers bluish purple, changing in colour to reddish purple in age, 5-7 cm in diameter, actinomorphic, showy; bracts 2, linear to elliptic, 1 cm long; pedicles 3.5-5 cm long, hirsute. Sepals 5, free, lanceolate to ovate, subequal, 1.5-2 cm long, acuminate at the apex, appressed-hairy outside. Corolla funnel shaped, 5-lobed; tube 3.5-4.8 cm by 1-1.5 cm, bluish purple with paler mid-petaline bands; lobes 2-2.6 cm by 2- 2.6 cm, rounded. Stamens 5, free, adnate to the corolla tube, included; filaments filiform, unequal, 1.5-2.5 cm long, dilated at the base, with curled hairs; anthers ditheous, ovate-oblong, white. Ovary superior, ovoid, 1.5-2.5 cm long, glabrous, trilocular, with 2 ovules in each locule on the axile placentae; style 2.5-3 cm long, stigmas bilobed, globose, white. Capsules globose, 6-10 mm by 6-8 mm, 4-6 seeded, glabrous. Seeds 5-7 mm long, black.

Distribution : Although probably an American tropical species, this population is now pantropical (Austin as cited in Dassanayake, 1980). Kress *et al.* (2003) cited this species as *Ipomoea learii* Paxton. and cultivated species in the checklist of Myanmar.

Uses : *Ipomoea indica* has been widely cultivated as a garden ornamental. This delicate flowers has a great market value because of the varying colors and shapes. The morning glory plant to be of essential medicinal use due to its seeds laxative properties. Morning glory not only attracts but hallucinate as well. Its has varied usage because of its hallucinating characteristics. All parts as purgative; stem/leaves crushed as a poultice for wounds and sores. Juice of roots, leaves, stem and flowers used as a laxative, and in treating broken bones.

Solanaceae (Juss. 1789)

10. *Brugmansia suaveolens* (Humb. & Bonpl. ex Willd) Bercht & Presl, Rostl.1. Solan (e) ac. 45. 1823.

Myanmar name	-	Padaing-gyi, Plate 1 (J)
English name	-	Angel' s Trumpet
Flowering period	-	March to May

Perennial, erect shrubs; 2-3 m high, stems and branches terete, brittle, minutely pubescent when young. Leaves simple, alternate, exstipulate; petioles 2-7 cm long, shortly tomentose; blades ovate-elliptic, 5-20 cm by 6-10 cm, cuneate at the base, sinuate-lobes along the margin, acuminate at the apex, membranous, tomentose on both surfaces. Flowers axillary and solitary, pendulous, white or creamy-white, 18 cm in diameter, actinomorphic, pedicels 7.2 cm long, tomentose. Calyx long tubular, 5-lobed, spathe-like, membranous, glandular pubescent, persistent; tube 13 cm long; lobes lanceolate, 1.5 cm long, acuminate. Corolla trumpet-shaped, with 5 acumes; tube 25 cm long, distinctly angled or grooved at the base; lobes strongly plicate in bud, glandular pubescent. Stamens 5, free, inserted, adnate to the base of corolla-tube; filaments slender, 15 cm long, white; anther ditheous, oblong-linear, 3 cm long, villous along the margins. Disk annular. Ovary superior, ovoid, 1 mm long, bilocular, with many ovules in each locule on the axile placentae; style filiform, 3.5 cm long, glabrous; stigma bifid. Capsules fusiform, 15 cm long, many seeded. Seeds oblongoid, 9 mm diameter.

Distribution : Native of coastal rainforest in SE. Brazil (Hepper as cited in Dassanayake, 1987). Kress *et al.* (2003) treated this species as *Datura suaveolens* Humb. and cultivated one in Myanmar.

Uses : The flowers and the seeds are traditionally used, mixed in water and ingested for its analgesia-like effect. *Brugmansia* are most often grown today as flowering ornamental plants. Traditional external uses have included the treating of aches and pains, dermatitis, arthritis, rheumatism, headaches, infection, and as an anti-inflammatory.

A. *Argemone mexicana* L.

B. *Fragaria vesca* L.

C. *Crateva magna* (Lour.) DC.

D. *Plumbago zeylanica* L.

E. *Buddleja asiatica* Lour.

F. *Jacaranda ovalifolia* R.Br.

G. *Pyrostegia venusta* Miers.

H. *Clerodendrum viscosum* Vent.

I. *Ipomoea indica* (Burf.) Merr.

J. *Brugmansia suaveolens* (Humb. & Bonpl. ex Willd) Bercht & Presl.

Discussion and Conclusion

The present floristic study deals with the plants growing in Kalaw area. Totally, 10 species belonging to 10 genera of 9 families under subclass Magnoliidae had been studied in the present paper. All the species presented in this study are dicotyledonous plants.

The families in this research paper are Papaveraceae, Plumbaginaceae, Capparaceae, Rosaceae, Solanaceae, Convolvulaceae, Verbenaceae, Loganiaceae, Bignoniaceae and under the subclass Magnoliidae. They are arranged according to the classification of APG III system, 2009.

Among the species in the present study, the species of *Fragaria vesca* L. is commonly found in this area. The species of *Plumbago zeylannica* L. is rarely found. Among the 10 species, *Argemone mexicana* L. and *Crateva magna* (Lour.) DC. are parietal placentation, *Plumbago zeylanica* L. and *Fragaria vesca* L. are pendulous placentation while the others are axile placentation. *Pyrostegia venusta* Miers. is tendrillar climber, *Argemone mexicana* L., *Fragaria vesca* L. and *Ipomoea indica* (Burf.) Merr. are herb, *Crateva magna* (Lour.) DC., and *Jacaranda ovalifolia* R.Br. are trees, the rest species are shrubs. Except *Crateva magna* (Lour.) DC., *Fragaria vesca* L., *Jacaranda ovalifolia* R.Br. and *Pyrostegia venusta* Miers. are compound leaves and others are simple. Flower of, *Clerodendrum viscosum* Vent., *Jacaranda ovalifolia* R.Br. and *Pyrostegia venusta* Miers. are zygomorphic, but the rest species are actinomorphic. The fruits of *Crateva magna* (Lour.) DC. is berry, *Fragaria vesca* L. is etaerio of achenes and *Clerodendrum viscosum* Vent. is drupe but those of others species are capsule.

Crateva magna (Lour.) DC. and , *Fragaria vesca* L. are found in the study area used for edible. *Ipomoea indica* (Burf.) Merr., *Plumbago indica* L., *Brugmansia suaveolens* (Humb. & Bonpl. ex Willd) Bercht & Presl., *Jacaranda ovalifolia* R.Br. and *Pyrostegia venusta* Miers. are used for ornamental plants. All 10 species are also medicinally important plants.

According to the data collected, it can be noted that 10 species from 10 genera are distributing. The collected species are identified and described with comments on their scientific names, Myanmar names, uses and coloured plates. It is hoped that this research of present investigation have contributed towards a better understanding of 10 species distributed in Kalaw area for its paper utilization in the other researchers. Finally, it is also hoped that this research paper will be very useful for various purposes.

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